

DEVELOPMENT AND STANDARDIZATION OF ACADEMIC SELF-EFFICACY SCALE FOR ADOLESCENTS

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Abstract

An attempt has been made to construct and standardize the Academic self-efficacy scale for adolescent students. A well structured scale was administered among them. The sample consists of 100 senior secondary school students randomly selected from senior secondary English medium schools situated in district Rewari, Haryana. Initially it was constructed with 57 statements covering five areas related to academic self-efficacy of school students. The scale was standardized using 't' test and finally 36 statements were retained for the final study. The present research discusses about the development of the scale to measure the level academic self-efficacy in senior secondary school students. The Scale consisted of 36 items representing distinctive academic behaviors on which subjects are supposed to rate their degree of confidence on five dimensions i.e. (A) Items pertaining to Self-efficacy in enlisting social resources, (B) Items pertaining to Self-efficacy in self-regulated learning (C) Items pertaining to Self-efficacy in class participation. (D) Items pertaining to Self-efficacy in time-management. (E) Items pertaining to Self-efficacy in study and examination. A five-point Likert-type scale measures responses ranging from 'extremely confident' to 'extremely not confident'. Higher scores indicate higher Academic Self-efficacy. The validity of the scale was content validity and reliability ranges from 0.82 to 0.93

INTRODUCTION

Every child is born with certain natural and inherited endowments. These endowments are modified and sublimated for making the individual child a useful member of society. Merely, possessing knowledge and skills does not mean that one will use them effectively under difficult condition (Bandura, 1986). Only those who are more self efficacious about being able to effectively manage and cope with these circumstances are expected to have probability of succeeding even if others have the same inherent ability or skill level.

Different researches have documented that students having stronger or higher level of Self-efficacy beliefs tend to have better feelings; persist for achievement; persevere longer while facing difficulties and encourage themselves to act accordingly. Students with higher levels of Self-efficacy believe that setbacks or failures are temporary which they can handle. They use all possible means or solutions to handle difficult situations and persist on their course of actions. They are not threatened by difficult tasks rather they consider the difficult tasks as a chance to learn and master new ways of doing things (Bandura, 1997, 1994; Schunk, 1995; Pajares, 2002).

On the other side, students having weak sense of developed Self-efficacy beliefs may not be interested in performing a task, feel frightened or threatened while facing difficulties and try to escape from difficult situations. They are less inclined towards their set goals and try to hide from cognitive tasks. Thus, these researches have revealed that Self-efficacy beliefs affect effort, goal setting, task choice, flexibility, determination and achievements.

Academic Self-efficacy refers to “an individual's belief (conviction) that they can successfully achieve at a designated level on an academic task or attain a specific academic goal”.

(Bandura, 1997; Eccles &

Wigfield, 2002; Elias & Loomis, 2002; Gresham, 1988; Linnenbrink & Pintrich, 2002a; Schunk & Pajares, 2002). Self-efficacy has been studied extensively, within multiple areas such as academics, career, social, health and athletics (Bandura, 1997). Academic Self-efficacy is pertinent to the context of academia and focuses on a person's belief about themselves regarding academic tasks. Therefore, “the self-efficacy which is pertinent in academic setting is academic self-efficacy, an individual's self evaluation of his/her capabilities and chances for success in the academic setting” (Robbins et al., 2004).

BRIEF REVIEW OF VARIOUS TOOLS FOR ASSESSING ACADEMIC SELF-EFFICACY

The Generalized Self-Efficacy Scale (GSE) (Tipton & Worthington, 1984) measures people's expectations that they can perform competently across a broad range of situations which are challenging and require effort and perseverance.

The instrument consists of 10 items, with a total possible score of 70 (e.g., "Once I set my mind to a task, almost nothing can stop me"). The total score was used as a self-efficacy measure. On this scale, a lower response indicates higher self-efficacy. Internal consistency for the GSE is .77 (Lennings, 1994). Tipton and Worthington (1984) found evidence of construct

validity when people with low GSE scores expended more effort and persevered longer on two tasks than did people with high GSE scores.

Academic Self-Efficacy Scale (Chemers, Hu, & Garcia, 2001). The Academic Self-Efficacy Scale (Chemers et al., 2001) was used to measure academic self-efficacy.

The scale consists of 8 items on a 7 point Likert-type scale from 1 (*Very Untrue*) to 7 (*Very True*). Points 2 to 6 were not labeled. Participants were asked to rate on a 1 to 7 scale how well they believe they perform certain academic tasks. Participants were asked questions such as “I know how to schedule my time to accomplish my tasks.” Chemers et al. (2001) obtained a Cronbach’s alpha reliability coefficient of .81 for the scale in their study of 373 undergraduates. Cronbach’s alpha reliability coefficient was .86.

Participants who scored above the mean were deemed as having high academic self-efficacy. Participants who scored below the mean were deemed as having low academic self-efficacy. According to Chemers et al. (2001), the measure appears to have high validity.

The Children’s Perceived Self-Efficacy Scale (Bandura, 1990; Bandura et al., 1996) comprises 37 items representing seven domains of functioning that form three basic efficacy factors - academic, selfregulatory, and social self-efficacy. For each item, participants rated their belief in their level of capability to execute the designated activities using a 6-point response format ranging from not at all to extremely well (1 = Not at all, 2 = Not too well, 3 = Okay, 4 = Pretty well, 5 = Very well, 6 = Extremely well).

- Perceived academic self-efficacy measures children’s perceived capability to judge their own learning, master academic subjects, and fulfill personal, parental, and teacher’s academic expectations. Examples of items include “How well can you concentrate on school subjects? and How well can you study when there are other interesting things to do?”
- Perceived self-regulatory efficacy measures children’s perceived capability to resist peer pressure, and to resist pressure to engage in high risk activities. Item examples include “How well can you resist peer pressure to do things in school that get you in trouble?; and How well can you stop yourself from skipping school when you feel bored or upset?”
- Perceived social self-efficacy measures children’s capability for peer relationships, selfassertiveness, and leisure time activities. Examples of items include “How well can you make and keep friends of the opposite sex?; and How well can you participate in class discussions?”

Bandura et al. (1996) established the three factors to be highly reliable (.87 for academic self-efficacy, .75 for social self-efficacy, and .80 for self-regulatory efficacy) constituting 15.7%, 8.3%, and 7.1% of the variance respectively. In the present research, 11 of the 37 original items were not included due to low factor loadings in the initial analysis by Bandura et al. (1996); however, internal reliabilities were still shown to be high for all three scales (0.89 for academic self-efficacy, 0.81 for social self-efficacy, and 0.82 for self-regulatory self-efficacy).

NEED OF DEVELOPING THE SCALE

Keeping in view the necessity of research work on Academic self-efficacy on adolescents, the investigator scanned the catalogues of different educational psychological tests published by various test publishers and found that no such scale is available in Indian conditions. A review of scales/questionnaires used to access the academic self-efficacy reveals that the existing tools were not appropriate to serve the purpose of present study. The reasons are as under:

- All the scales/Questionnaires have been standardized in western culture.
- The sample used for the standardization of the scales was culturally biased as it was picked from western countries.

Therefore, the investigator realized the need to standardize a scale to access academic self-efficacy.

Following steps were followed for the development and standardization of academic self-efficacy scale.

PLANNING THE SCALE

Planning stage of the scale tries to answer what content area is to be covered the scale? What type of items are to be included in the scale and what are the objectives that are going to be measured? The items of academic self-efficacy scale were selected from academic efficacy behavior revealed by the students to the investigator during interview session. the scale was planned to act as self- reporting paper pencil test.

OBJECTIVES OF THE SCALE

The major objective of construction of Academic Self-efficacy scale was to develop a self-reported paper pencil test to access academic self-efficacy of the students in the age group of 11-17 years studying in secondary and senior secondary classes under Indian conditions.

IDENTIFICATION OF THE AREAS AND GENERATION OF THE ITEMS

A number of books, journals and encyclopedias were reviewed to get the required knowledge for framing the items for the scale. Experts' opinion was also sought for constructing the items of the scale, after which 57 items pertaining to the Academic Self-efficacy were drafted. These items were categorized into **five** sub-scales:

- Items pertaining to Self-efficacy in enlisting social resources.
- Items pertaining to Self-efficacy in self-regulated learning.
- Items pertaining to Self-efficacy in class participation.
- Items pertaining to Self-efficacy in time-management.
- Items pertaining to Self-efficacy in study and examination.

FIRST DRAFT

Experienced professionals associated with Education were consulted. Based on the qualitative analysis of the response from different sources and reviewing of literature available on Academic Self-efficacy, initially 57 items were generated pertaining to these five dimensions

- **First dimension** i.e. self-efficacy in **enlisting social resources**, consisted of **11 items** related with self-efficacy in dealing social situations in the school like getting help from teachers and friends etc.
- **Second dimension** i.e. self-efficacy in **self-regulated learning**, consisted of **15 items** related to self-efficacy in being a responsible learner.
- **Third dimension** i.e. self-efficacy in **class-participation**, consisted of **9 items** related to self-efficacy in participating in class activities.
- **Fourth dimension** i.e. self-efficacy in **time-management**; consisted of **7 items** related to self-efficacy in managing the time well for class and home work.
- **Fifth dimension** i.e. self-efficacy in **study and examination**, consisted **15 items** related to self-efficacy in dealing with examination and learning techniques.

SECOND DRAFT

The first draft of 57 items was given to 15 experts in the field of education and psychology requesting them to mention against item whether the items were relevant to Academic self-efficacy and were consistent with the dimensions. In the light of comments received from them, some of the items were modified or changed keeping in view the suggestions received from them

DIMENSIONS OF ACADEMIC SELF-EFFICACY AND NO. OF ITEMS IN FIRST AND SECOND DRAFT SHORTLISTED

Dimensions of the Scale	No. of items in First Draft	No. of items in Second Draft
Self-efficacy in enlisting social resources	11	11
Self-efficacy in Self-regulated learning	15	10
Self-efficacy in class participation	9	9
Self-efficacy in time management	7	6
Self-efficacy in study and examination	15	9
Total No. of items	57	45

FIRST TRY OUT

The second draft of the scale with 45 items was administered to a sample of 20 adolescent English Medium students of Jain Public Senior Secondary School, Rewari studying in 11TH class to check the language and any ambiguity in the items of the scale. The investigator administered this scale to know the deficiencies of the scale and difficulties faced by the students in responding to the items. After the second draft, minor changes were made in the language of some items depending upon the feedback received from the students. **SECOND**

TRY OUT

The purpose of second try-out was to get data for determining the discriminating value of the items. This also helped to determine the number items to be included in the final draft of the scale. For the purpose of item analysis the numbers of students included were 100. In order to determine the homogeneity and applicability of the items, the scale was administered to a group of 100 adolescent students randomly selected in the age group of 12 to 17 years studying in secondary and senior secondary classes studying in various English medium schools of Rewari District. The students were encouraged to answer each item with honesty by assuring

them that their responses would be kept confidential and will be used only for research purpose. There was no time limit. The item was to be rated on five points Likert type scale i.e. extremely not confident, hardly confident, confident, fairly confident and extremely not confident, ranging from 4 to 0.

PROCEDURE OF ITEM ANALYSIS

The item analysis was carried out under the following steps:-

- Firstly, all the 100 responded sheets were arranged in ascending order from lower score at the top to higher score at the bottom.
- Secondly, 27 low score responded sheets and 27 high score responded sheets were taken into consideration to ascertain the internal consistency of the constructed 45 items. The data was analyzed by using Mean, S.D, and t-test. The significance difference between 27% lower and 27% upper group on each item was ascertained.

Mean difference between lower 27% and upper 27% items of ASES (Academic Self-efficacy scale for Adolescents)

Items	Upper		Lower		t-value	Significant/ Non-Significant
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D		
1	4.33	0.86	3.22	1.1	4.11	S
2	4.07	1.05	3.6	0.9	1.767	NS
3	4.07	1.02	3.74	1.2	1.09	NS
4	3.89	1.03	3.33	1.22	1.83	NS
5	4.11	0.92	3.26	1.14	3.04	S
6	2.33	1.09	2.11	1.1	0.738	NS
7	4.00	0.82	3.48	1.07	2.00	NS
8	4.44	0.96	2.56	1.4	5.78	S
9	4.59	0.62	3.22	1.2	5.29	S
10	3.93	0.98	2.67	1.15	4.36	S
11	3.81	1.02	2.74	1.11	3.70	S
12	3.85	1.01	3.0	1.15	2.88	S

13	4.74	0.44	3.44	1.1	5.70	S
14	3.85	0.8	2.59	1.13	4.74	S
15	4.52	0.63	3.04	1.23	5.56	S
16	4.44	0.74	2.74	1.11	7.76	S
17	4.93	0.26	3.48	1.23	5.99	S
18	4.85	0.36	3.52	0.83	7.64	S
19	4.48	0.74	3.07	0.98	5.97	S
20	4.04	0.64	2.44	0.79	8.205	S
21	4.07	0.9	2.93	0.98	4.47	S
22	3.3	0.9	1.89	1.03	5.36	S
23	4.59	0.56	3.3	1.15	5.24	S
24	4.41	0.83	2.78	1.17	5.95	S
25	3.04	1.00	2.44	1.29	1.90	NS
26	3.96	0.96	3.3	1.15	2.27	NS
27	3.33	1.19	2.3	1.08	3.34	S
28	4.04	0.64	2.96	0.84	5.35	S
29	4.04	0.84	3.3	0.97	2.99	S
30	4.81	0.47	3.37	1.19	5.87	S
31	4.63	0.73	2.63	0.82	9.57	S
32	4.78	0.5	2.96	1.1	7.84	S
33	4.44	0.5	3.22	1.07	5.40	S
34	4.48	0.63	3.04	1.00	6.34	S
35	4.67	0.82	3.22	0.83	6.47	S
36	3.93	1.02	3.78	1.13	0.52	NS
37	3.93	0.6	2.89	0.79	5.48	S
38	4.48	0.57	3.07	1.18	5.62	S
39	3.67	0.77	2.22	0.83	6.68	S
40	3.52	0.92	2.85	1.04	2.50	NS

41	4.22	0.68	2.93	0.83	6.29	S
42	4.67	0.82	3.3	0.94	5.69	S
43	4.85	0.36	3.22	0.99	8.04	S
44	4.59	0.49	3.22	1.07	6.06	S
45	4.15	0.59	2.7	1.01	6.44	S

FINAL DRAFT

Out of 45 items, **36 items** were found significant either at .01 or .05 levels of significance. Items number 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 25, 26, 36 and 40 were not found significant and had to be dropped out. Thus, total

9 items which were not significant were removed from the scale and remaining 36 items under five dimensions were further evaluated by computing items-total correlation. The obtained values shown in table indicate high homogeneity among the items constructed to constitute the scale.

TOTAL ITEM CORRELATION OF ACADEMIC SELF-EFFICACY SCALE

Item	Correlation	Item	Correlation	Item	Correlation	Item	Correlation
1	0.482**	10	0.537**	19	0.428**	28	0.584**
2	0.238**	11	0.416**	20	0.360**	29	0.384**
3	0.272**	12	0.405**	21	0.551**	30	0.420**
4	0.341**	13	0.580**	22	0.554**	31	0.527**
5	0.323**	14	0.464**	23	0.489**	32	0.519**
6	0.406**	15	0.567**	24	0.565**	33	0.521**
7	0.465**	16	0.578**	25	0.527**	34	0.555**
8	0.441**	17	0.409**	26	0.501**	35	0.412**
9	0.511**	18	0.506**	27	0.631**	36	0.493**

INTER-CORRELATIONS AMONG THE ITEMS OF ACADEMIC SELF-EFFICACY SCALE

Dimensions	Self-Efficacy in Enlisting social Resources (A)	Self-Efficacy in Self-regulated learning (B)	Self-Efficacy in Class Participation (C)	Self-Efficacy in Time Management (D)	Self-Efficacy in Study and Examination (E)	Total (T)
Self-Efficacy in Enlisting social Resources (A)	rAA 1	-	-	-	-	-
Self-Efficacy in Self-regulated learning (B)	rAB 0.438	rBB 1	-	-	-	-
Self-Efficacy in Class Participation (C)	rAC 0.429	rBC 0.632	rCC 1	-	-	-
Self-Efficacy in Time Management (D)	rAD 0.344	rBD 0.687	rCD 0.561	rDD 1	-	-
Self-Efficacy in Study and Examination (E)	rAE 0.408	rBE 0.581	rCE 0.586	rDE 0.594	rEE 1	-
Total (T)	rAT 0.634	rBT 0.874	rCT 0.813	rDT 0.804	rET 0.807	1

CODE AND DIMENSIONS OF ACADEMIC SELF-EFFICACY SCALE

Dimensions of Academic Self-Efficacy	Code	Item Numbers	Total Items
Self-Efficacy in Enlisting social Resources	A	1-6	6
Self-Efficacy in Self-regulated learning	B	7-16	10
Self-Efficacy in Class Participation	C	17-23	7
Self-Efficacy in Time Management	D	24-28	5
Self-Efficacy in Study and Examination	E	29-36	8

RELIABILITY OF THE SCALE

	SAMPLE (N)	Spearman-Brown Reliability Index	Guttman Reliability	split-half
Academic Self-efficacy	200	0.825	0.93	

VALIDITY OF THE SCALE

Validity is a concern for relationship between, on the one hand, the purpose set to achieve, and on the other hand, the efforts taken, the means employed and what these efforts and means actually achieve. The validity of academic Self-Efficacy Scale constructed was tested on the basis of face validity and content validity.

The scale was validated against the criterion of content validity. All the 36 items were presented to five judges for their opinion and items were found to be consistent with Academic self-Efficacy.

Therefore, on the basis of face validity and content validity, it appears reasonable to agree that Academic Self-efficacy scale measures degree of Academic Self-efficacy among adolescents.

INSTRUCTIONS FOR FILLING UP THE SCALE

Students were told that there is no 'right' or 'wrong' answer, only their honest response is important. Following instructions were written on the scale to clarify the meaning in most simple language.

*In the following pages there are 36 statements related to you. Read the statements carefully and encircle the appropriate option you strongly agree with. Encircle only one option to describe your degree of confidence with each statement– 1. **Extremely not Confident**, 2. **Hardly Confident**, 3. **Confident**, 4. **Fairly Confident**, 5. **Extremely confident**. There is no time limit but try to complete as early as possible. Your answer will remain confidential and used only for research purpose. The Scale is part of investigation effort to bring reforms in education system. The success of research depends on your cooperation. So answer quickly without any hesitation. Kindly get your doubts clarified and ensure that all the statements have been responded.*

INSTRUCTIONS FOR ADMINISTERING THE SCALE

- Introduce yourself to maintain friendly relationship.
- Ask the students to sit comfortably.
- Tell the students the purpose of the test and importance of their true response for the study.
- Ensure them that their responses will remain confidential and try to invoke honesty in responding.
- Distribute the consumable booklet of Academic Self-efficacy scale to each adolescent student.
- Ask them to supply necessary information in the space provided in the consumable booklet.
- Read the instructions clearly from the booklet and invite them to clear any doubts before they start responding.
- Ask them to respond independently and truly.
- Supervise them by moving around in the room.
- Clarify the meaning of certain items if needed.
- Collect the consumable booklets back and ensure that all the entries have been filled and all the items have been responded.

INTERPRETATION AND CLASSIFICATION OF RAW SCORES FOR ALL DIMENSIONS

- $M \pm SD$
- Percentile Norms
- Z-Scores

SCORING PROCEDURE OF RESPONSES FOR ACADEMIC SELF-EFFICACY SCALE FOR ADOLESCENTS

Responses	Scores
Extremely Confident	4
Fairly Confident	3
Confident	2
Hardly Confident	1
Extremely Not Confident	0

NO. OF ITEMS AND SCORES ON EACH DIMENSION OF ASEA

Dimensions of Academic Self-efficacy	Total No. of Items	Maximum Score
Self-Efficacy in Enlisting social Resources	6	24
Self-Efficacy in Self-regulated learning	10	40
Self-Efficacy in Class Participation	7	28
Self-Efficacy in Time Management	5	20
Self-Efficacy in Study and Examination	8	32
Total	36	144

INTERPRETATION OF SCORES

Range of Academic Raw Scores	Self-efficacy Category	Interpretation
105-144	High	
65-104	Average	
64 and below	Low	

INTERPRETATION OF RAW SCORES WITH THE HELP OF Z-SCORES

Raw Score	Z-Score						
40	-2.27 σ	62	-1.16 σ	84	-0.05 σ	106	1.06 σ
41	-2.22 σ	63	1.11 σ	85	0.00 σ	107	1.11 σ
42	-2.17 σ	64	-1.06 σ	86	0.05 σ	108	1.16 σ
43	-2.12 σ	65	-1.01 σ	87	0.10 σ	109	1.21 σ
44	-2.07 σ	66	-0.95 σ	88	0.15 σ	110	1.26 σ
45	-2.02 σ	67	-0.90 σ	89	0.20 σ	111	1.31 σ
46	-1.96 σ	68	-0.85 σ	90	0.25 σ	112	1.36 σ
47	-1.91 σ	69	-0.80 σ	91	0.30 σ	113	1.41 σ
48	-1.86 σ	70	-0.75 σ	92	0.35 σ	114	1.46 σ
49	-1.81 σ	71	-0.70 σ	93	0.40 σ	115	1.51 σ
50	-1.76 σ	72	-0.65 σ	94	0.45 σ	116	1.56 σ
51	-1.71 σ	73	-0.60 σ	95	0.50 σ	117	1.61 σ
52	-1.66 σ	74	-0.55 σ	96	0.55 σ	118	1.66 σ
53	-1.61 σ	75	-0.50 σ	97	0.60 σ	119	1.71 σ
54	-1.56 σ	76	-0.45 σ	98	0.65 σ	120	1.76 σ
55	-1.51 σ	77	-0.40 σ	99	0.70 σ	121	1.81 σ
56	-1.46 σ	78	-0.35 σ	100	0.75 σ	122	1.86 σ
57	-1.41 σ	79	-0.30 σ	101	0.80 σ	123	1.91 σ
58	-1.36 σ	80	-0.25 σ	102	0.85 σ	124	1.96 σ
59	-1.31 σ	81	-0.20 σ	103	0.90 σ	125	2.02 σ
60	-1.26 σ	82	-0.15 σ	104	0.95 σ	126	2.07 σ
61	-1.21 σ	83	-0.10 σ	105	1.01 σ	127	2.12 σ

NORMS FOR INTERPRETATION ON THE BASIS OF Z-SCORES

Sr. No.	Range of z-Scores	Grade	Levels of Academic Self-efficacy
1.	+2.01 σ and above	A	Excellent
2.	+1.26 σ to +2.00 σ	B	High
3.	+0.50 σ to +1.25 σ	C	Above Average
4	-0.50 σ to +0.50 σ	D	Moderate
5.	-0.51 σ to +1.25 σ	E	Below Average
6.	-1.26 σ to -2.00 σ	F	Low
7.	-2.01 σ and below	G	Very Poor

INTERPRETATION ON THE BASIS OF PERCENTILE NORMS

Percentiles	Raw scores	Interpretation
P90	113.3	Very High Academic Self-efficacy
P80	103	
P75 (Q3)	102	High Academic self-efficacy
P70	98.3	
P60	87.5	
P50 (Median)	82	Average Academic Self-efficacy
P40	77	
P30	70	
P25 (Q1)	70	Low Academic Self-efficacy
P20	68	
P10	60.9	Very Low Academic Self-efficacy

CONCLUSION

The investigator is hopeful that this scale would be helpful to measure the academic self-efficacy levels of school students and student's academic self-efficacy can provide teachers with important insights. To help struggling learners with low self-efficacy, and get them to invest sufficient effort and persist on challenging tasks, teachers must systematically develop high self-efficacy within these students. They can help strengthen the self-efficacy of struggling learners by:

- Linking new work to recent successes
- Reinforcing effort and persistence
- Stressing peer modeling
- Teaching struggling learners to make facilitative attributions
- Helping struggling learners identify or create personally important goals

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